

FINANCIAL PERFORMANCE MEASUREMENT OF COMPANIES IN THE BIST WITH SITDE AND RAWEC METHODS

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Abstract: This study aims to evaluate the financial performance of 36 companies from different sectors listed on Borsa Istanbul (BIST) Sustainability Index for the years 2021, 2022, and 2023 using multi-criteria decision-making (MCDM) methods. BIST companies represent Turkey's most actively traded and transparent companies. These companies constitute a suitable sample for our study because they provide reliable and accessible financial data and include Turkey's largest and most institutionally developed companies. Eight financial criteria were selected as performance measures, namely Price-to-Earnings ratio (P/E), Return on Capital Employed (ROCE), Tobin's Q, Accounts Receivable Turnover, Operating Margin, Cost of Goods Sold, Market Capitalization, and Enterprise Value. The Similarity to Ideal-TOPSIS with Distance Entropy (SITDE) method was applied to objectively determine the weights of the criteria, while the Rank Aggregation with Weighted Entropy and Ideal Closeness (RAWEC) method was employed to rank the alternatives. The results of the study, in 2021, during the post-pandemic recovery, companies' ROCE and Accounts Receivable Turnover were the most influential

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criteria. Tobin's Q, reflecting long-term investor and market expectations, remained highly important across all years. In 2022 and 2023, Enterprise Value and Market Capitalization emerged as key factors, highlighting the impact of company size and investor confidence on financial performance.

Keywords: *Financial Performance; Borsa Istanbul; Multi-Criteria Decision-Making; Rank Aggregation with Weighted Entropy and Ideal Closeness.*

1. Introduction

Intensifying global competition, economic volatility, and increasing expectations for sustainable development have made it essential for businesses to be evaluated not only based on the quality of their products and services but also on the robustness of their financial structures. Financial performance has emerged as a critical indicator of a company's operational effectiveness, efficiency in resource utilization, and strategic resilience. No longer merely an accounting output, financial performance now serves as a vital decision-support tool for investors, creditors, stakeholders, and policymakers. A company's growth prospects, competitive positioning, and long-term sustainability increasingly depend on a comprehensive and multidimensional assessment of its financial performance (Demirbaşı et al., 2024; Zhang et al., 2025). Sustainability is one of the most important goals for companies. A comprehensive and multidimensional assessment of this potential financial performance is becoming increasingly important. Accurate and timely analyses have led to future growth prospects, a sustainable position, and long-term sustainability (Kaya et al., 2024; Sezgin et al., 2024).

Financial analysis is the process of applying analytical methods and techniques to financial statements (balance sheets, income statements) generated by a detailed accounting information system to assess the financial condition and ongoing operations (Sarioglu et al., 2025). The most frequently used method in this process is financial ratio analysis. A company uses financial ratios to increase its profitability, liquidity, and financial strength in the market (Eghbal et al., 2025). Ratio analysis allows all stakeholders (owners, investors, employees) to analyze a company's financial health. Financial ratios can also be used to compare the relative performance of companies within an index, within a sector, across sectors, within a company over years or across companies of different sizes (Delen et al., 2013).

In an environment where business models, technology, and organizational structures are constantly changing and evolving, it is vital to determine which criteria are more important in evaluating company performance. Furthermore, their performance should be compared to their competitors to enable strategic decisions and understand their current situation. Because multidimensional evaluations are considered a type of multi-criteria decision-making (MCDM) problem, they have been conducted using MCDM methods in recent years ((Bouraima et al., 2025; Koçak et al., 2025; Zaman et al., 2025). These methods make it possible to compare businesses in an unbiased manner (Razak et al., 2025).

In this study, 36 companies (excluding banks and financial institutions) included in the BIST Sustainability Index were analyzed between 2021, 2022 and 2023. The reasons for selecting the analyzed period are summarized below:

- Reflecting the recovery process of companies after COVID-19
- Comprehensively addressing the effects of global economic fluctuations on BIST companies
- The transition to inflation accounting in Turkey

To analyze the financial performance of the companies, P/E, ROCE, Tobin's Q, Receivables Turnover, Operating Profit Margin, Cost of Goods Sold, Market Value and Enterprise Value were determined as their salaries. These indicators are frequently used in the literature as powerful indicators that reflect the performance of companies.

This study's methodological innovation is seen in the way it ranks firm performance using the RAWEC method and determines criterion weights using the SITDE method. The relative weight of each criterion is taken into consideration, and performance ratings are combined in an improved and reasonable way, by combining these two methods. As a result, this research presents a financial analysis with an empirical framework based on an MCDM structure, going beyond traditional one-dimensional evaluation methodologies.

The results provide investors, business managers, and regulators with useful decision-making support in addition to illustrating the relative financial performance of the companies in the sample. The main objective of this research is to support stakeholders' strategic decision-making processes as well as the body of literature on financial analysis. A multidimensional assessment of financial performance enhances the ability to forecast not only current conditions but also the long-term sustainable success of firms.

2. Literature Review

Table 1 presents a comprehensive overview of 22 recent studies (2024–2025) that utilize various MCDM methods for evaluating financial or organizational performance across diverse sectors. In recent years, MCDM methods have been frequently used to evaluate financial performance in different sectors, indices, and countries. Previous studies show sectoral and methodological diversity.

[Katrancı et al. \(2025\)](#) applied the ITARA, COBRA, and AHP methods to the BIST 100 index in their study. [Mitra et al. \(2025\)](#) analyzed companies on the Indian stock exchange using the Best-Worst method. [Karki et al. \(2025\)](#) applied the R-SWARA and CoCoSo methods in the banking sector, while [Işık, Çalık, et al., 2025](#) used the Pythagorean fuzzy AHP and MAIRCA methods in financial performance analysis in the Turkish insurance sector. [Eyceyurt Batir and Babacan \(2025\)](#) analyzed Islamic banking using SWARA-AHP-COPRAS. In a similar study, [Işık, Adalar, et al. \(2025\)](#) analyzed Islamic banks using the SPC, SWARA, and AROMAN methods.

[Deng et al. \(2025\)](#) employed VIKOR, ANP, and DEMATEL in the pharmaceutical industry, [Ertuğrul & Özdarak, 2025](#) analyzed airline companies with MCDM techniques, and [Oubrahim & Sefiani, 2025](#) applied BWM and DEMATEL to airport performance. In the maritime industry, [Lin et al. \(2024\)](#) adopted Fuzzy DEMATEL. From a methodological perspective, novel approaches are introduced as well. [Biswas et al., 2025](#) implemented PRASIAS and LOPCOW, while [Veeramani et al. \(2025\)](#) utilized AHP, TOPSIS, and GRA comparatively, highlighting the application potential of

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both classical and emerging MCDM techniques.

Research has particularly focused on the BIST Sustainability Index. [Özekenci \(2024\)](#) applied LBWA and MEREC-based CRADIS to the BIST Sustainability 25 Index. [Barutbas et al. \(2024\)](#) assessed leading retail companies in BIST using fuzzy MCDM and DF-TOPSIS, and ([Sezgin et al., 2024](#)) examined the IT sector using MEREC and MARCOS.

[Alsanousi et al. \(2024\)](#) studied Saudi stocks using BWM and TOPSIS, while [Eghbal et al. \(2025\)](#) employed MULTI-MOORA and D-CRITIC for financial performance assessment. [Ergülen and Çalık \(2024\)](#) evaluated Turkey's top 500 industrial enterprises with F-BWM and MARCOS, whereas ([Hussain et al., 2024](#)) applied AHP, TOPSIS, and GRA in the banking sector.

Overall, the literature shows that a variety of MCDM techniques—most notably TOPSIS, AHP, DEMATEL, and MARCOS—have been extensively used across sectors. However, most studies rely on well-known classical methods, while fewer employ novel or hybrid approaches. Against this background, the present study makes two major contributions: first, by integrating SITDE and RAWEC methods, it offers a methodological innovation for financial performance evaluation; second, by focusing on the BIST Sustainability Index during the period 2021–2023, it provides a comprehensive analysis of the post-COVID recovery and the effects of global economic fluctuations, thereby addressing a critical gap in the literature.

Table 1: Literature Review

Authors	Methods	Index-Sector
Katranci et al. (2025)	ITARA, COBRA, AHP	BIST 100
Mitra et al. (2025)	BEST-WORST	Indian stock market
Karki et al. (2025)	MCDM, R-SWARA, CoCoSo	Banking
Işık, Çalık, et al. (2025)	Pythagorean fuzzy AHP, MAIRCA	Turkish insurance sector
Eyceyurt Batir and Babacan (2025)	SWARA-AHP-COPRAS	Islamic banking
Dang et al. (2019)	VIKOR, ANP, DEMATEL	Pharmaceutical Company
Ertuğrul and Özdarak (2025)	MCDM	Airline
Oubrahim and Sefiani (2025)	BWM, DEMATEL	Airport
Biswas et al. (2025)	PRASIAS, LOPCOW	-
Veeramani et al. (2025)	AHP, TOPSIS, GRA	-
Işık, Adalar, et al. (2025)	SPC, SWARA, AROMAN	Islamic banks
Özekenci (2024)	LBWA and MEREC-based CRADIS	BIST Sustainability 25 Index
Alsanousi et al. (2024)	MCDM; BWM; TOPSIS	Saudi stocks
Barutbaş et al. (2024)	Fuzzy MCDM; DF TOPSIS	Retail Companies in BIST
Sezgin et al. (2024)	MEREC, MARCOS	BIST IT sector
Ghaemi-Zadeh and Eghbali-Zarch (2024)	MULTI-MOORA, D -CRITIC	-
Liou et al. (2024)	DEMATEL, MCDM	-
Ergülen and Çalık (2024)	F-BWM, MARCOS	Türkiye's top 500 enterprises
Lin et al. (2024)	Fuzzy DEMATEL	Shipping companies
Hussain et al. (2024)	MCDM, AHP, TOPSIS, GRA	Banking

3. Methodology

In this study, banks and other financial institutions were excluded from the

companies listed on the BIST Sustainability Index in 2021, 2022, and 2023. A total of 36 companies with complete data available for the relevant period were included in the analysis. The period between 2021 and 2023 has been specifically chosen to take into account the recovery process of companies after the COVID-19 pandemic, the inflation accounting process in Turkey, and possible structural disruptions caused by unusual economic policies. It was evaluated using the SITDE-RAWEC hybrid method as a decision support framework. This hybrid method is structured into two stages. In Stage 1, criteria weights are determined using the SITDE method. In Stage 2, the RAWEC method is employed to evaluate and rank the alternatives' performance. Fig. 1 shows a flow chart of the method.

Figure 1: Steps of the hybrid model

3.1 SITDE-RAWEC Hybrid Method for Evaluation of Financial Performance

SITDE, developed by Gopisetty and Sama (2025), is a MCDM approach that addresses the limitations of traditional weighting methods by integrating data distribution characteristics—specifically skewness—into the evaluation process. Traditional MCDM techniques generally operate under the assumption of symmetric data distributions. However, real-world data is often asymmetric. Therefore, traditional techniques can lead to biased or misleading results. The SITDE method, used in this study, increases the reliability and validity of the decision-making process by

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systematically adjusting the criteria weights according to their skewness. Using this method, the impact of distributional bias is reduced. The SITDE criterion weighting method more accurately reflects the effects of criteria with high skewness values at the decision-making process. Thus, it significantly increases objectivity and robustness in the weighting of criteria in complex models containing asymmetric data (Gopisetty & Sama, 2025; Kamruddin et al., 2025).

The SITDE method helps reduce biases arising from asymmetric data. Unlike other traditional criterion weighting methods, it produces more balanced and objective results. The skewness coefficients used to re-adjust criterion weights in the decision-making process with the SITDE method capture the extent to which a distribution deviates from symmetry. Thus, the method also takes into account the risk of bias created by criteria with high levels of skewness, often due to outliers in the data set. As the skewness coefficient increases, the weight of the relevant criterion is reduced or balanced to reduce skewness in the distribution. Conversely, criteria with lower skewness receive relatively more weight because they more accurately capture the central tendency of the data. Thus, in the SITDE method, criterion weights are aligned with the fundamental distribution characteristics of the data, thereby enhancing the objectivity and robustness of the evaluations.

The RAWEC method recently proposed by Puška et al. (2024) is an MCDM approach designed to simplify the decision-making process by reducing computational complexity. Unlike other traditional MCDM techniques, which typically have a complex structure, the RAWEC method is simpler and more accessible. The key innovation of this method lies in the use of dual normalization procedures that transform criteria into both “the larger, the better” and “the smaller, the better” formats. This dual normalization procedure enhances the consistency and reliability of evaluations by appropriately considering the directional characteristics of each criterion (Katranci et al., 2025; Trung et al., 2024). As a result, RAWEC is not only more accurate and efficient but also more practical. Its advantage stems primarily from the binary normalization strategy, which effectively reflects the directional characteristics of the criteria, reduces computational steps, and enhances evaluation precision.

In this study, a hybrid decision support system, SITDE-RAWEC, is developed and proposed for financial performance let $A = \{A_1, A_2, \dots, A_i, \dots, A_m\}$ ($i = 1, 2, \dots, m$) indicate the alternatives, $C = \{C_1, C_2, \dots, C_j, \dots, C_n\}$ ($j = 1, 2, \dots, n$) represents the criteria. This hybrid method comprises two stages, and the steps of the method are outlined as follows:

Stage 1: Calculating the weights of the criteria with the SITDE method.

Step 1-1: Initially, a decision matrix is constructed to evaluate the performance of alternatives based on predefined criteria.

$$= \begin{bmatrix} X_{11} & X_{12} & \dots & X_{1j} & \dots & X_{1n} \\ X_{21} & X_{22} & \dots & X_{2j} & \dots & X_{2n} \\ \vdots & \vdots & \ddots & \vdots & \ddots & \vdots \\ X_{i1} & X_{i2} & \dots & X_{ij} & \dots & X_{in} \\ \vdots & \vdots & \ddots & \vdots & \ddots & \vdots \\ X_{m1} & X_{m2} & \dots & X_{mj} & \dots & X_{mn} \end{bmatrix} \quad (1)$$

Step 1-2: The decision matrix in Eq. (1) is normalized by Eq. (2).

$$N_{ij} = \begin{cases} \frac{\min(x_{ij})}{x_{ij}}, & \text{for benefit criteria} \\ \frac{x_{ij}}{\max(x_{ij})}, & \text{for cost criteria} \end{cases}; (i = 1, \dots, m; j = 1, \dots, n). \quad (2)$$

Step 1-3: The skewness matrix elements are obtained with Eq. (3).

$$S_j = \frac{n}{(n-1)(n-2)} \sum_j^n \frac{N_{ij} - \bar{N}_j}{\sigma_j}. \quad (3)$$

Herein \bar{N}_j indicates the average value calculated for each criterion and σ_j indicates the standard deviation for each criterion.

Step 1-4: The skewness matrix is normalized with Eq. (4).

$$S_j^N = \log \left| \left((S_j + 1) + (|\min(S_j)| + 1) \right) \right|. \quad (4)$$

Step 1-5: Eq. (5) is used to calculate the importance of the criteria.

$$w_j = \frac{S_j^N}{\sum_{j=1}^n S_j^N}. \quad (5)$$

Stage 2: Ranking the alternatives through the RAWEC method.

Step 2-1: Initially, a decision matrix is constructed to evaluate the performance of alternatives based on predefined criteria.

Step 2-2: The decision matrix in Eq. (1) is normalized by two different methods. Eq. (6) & Eq. (7) are used to perform these operations.

$$N^{1st}_{ij} = \begin{cases} N^{1st(+)}_{ij} = \frac{x_{ij}}{\max(x_{ij})}; & \text{for benefit criteria} \\ N^{1st(-)}_{ij} = \frac{\min(N_{X_{ij}})}{x_{ij}}; & \text{for cost criteria} \end{cases}. \quad (6)$$

$$N^{2nd}_{ij} = \begin{cases} N^{2nd(+)}_{ij} = \frac{\min(x_{ij})}{x_{ij}}; & \text{for benefit criteria} \\ N^{2nd(-)}_{ij} = \frac{x_{ij}}{\max(x_{ij})}; & \text{for cost criteria} \end{cases}. \quad (7)$$

Step 2-3: The deviation from the criterion weight matrix is processed through two distinct computational procedures, as defined in Eq. (8 and 9).

$$D^{1st}_i = \sum_{j=1}^n w_j (1 - N^{1st}_{ij}). \quad (8)$$

$$D^{2nd}_i = \sum_{j=1}^n w_j (1 - N^{2nd}_{ij}). \quad (9)$$

Step 2-4: The final ranking of alternatives value matrix is calculated by applying Eq. (10).

$$R_i = \frac{D^{2nd}_i - D^{1st}_i}{D^{2nd}_i + D^{1st}_i}. \quad (10)$$

4. Case Study

This study aims to evaluate the financial performance of 36 BIST Sustainability

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Index listed companies from various sectors over the years 2021, 2022, and 2023. Eight financial ratios were selected as criteria. The SITDE method was used to determine the criteria weights, while the RAWEC method was applied to rank the alternatives. The SITDE-RAWEC method was implemented using a decision matrix consisting of 8 criteria and 36 alternatives.

4.1 Criteria, and Alternatives

4.1.1 Identification of the Criteria

In the evaluation of the financial performance of companies in this study, eight criteria (“P/E”, “ROCE”, “Tobin Q”, “Accounts Receivable Turnover”, “Operating Margin”, “Cost of Goods Sold”, “Market Capitalization”, “Enterprise Value”) were determined. These criteria are as follows:

P/E (C1) – This criterion refers to the ratio of a company's share price to its earnings per share (EPS), indicating how much investors are willing to pay for one unit of earnings. The ratio captures both the company's current market valuation and investor expectations regarding future performance. A high P/E ratio typically reflects optimistic growth expectations, whereas a low P/E ratio may indicate either undervaluation or a heightened perception of risk. As such, the P/E ratio serves as a composite indicator that encompasses both rational investment expectations and psychological dynamics in the market (Park, 2021).

ROCE (C2) – This criterion, ROCE is a key indicator for evaluating a company's profitability and the efficiency with which it utilizes its capital. Specifically, it measures the amount of operating profit generated in relation to the total capital employed, encompassing both equity and debt. The ratio offers investors and managers a comprehensive perspective on not only short-term performance but also on capital efficiency and long-term financial sustainability. Firms with high ROCE values often adopt strategic practices that emphasize the efficient use of fixed assets, optimized working capital management, and robust operating margins (Rosario & Rosario, 2024).

Tobin Q (C3) – This criterion is a financial performance indicator (Subramanyam & Anand, 2025). Developed by economist James Tobin and indicates the firm's cost of repurchasing and remanufacturing. In other words, this ratio is the ratio of a firm's market value (the sum of its market capitalization and liabilities) to its replacement cost (the book value of its assets). This ratio indicates how much higher or lower the firm's market value of its assets is compared to its replacement cost. A Tobin's Q ratio greater than 1 indicates a high market value of its assets and a high ownership interest rate. A ratio less than 1 indicates a low market value of its assets (Tobin, 1969). This ratio is useful for assessing the extent to which intangible assets (reputation, technology, or brand value) are incorporated into a company's market valuation (Kroes et al., 2012).

Accounts Receivable Turnover (C4) – This criterion is a financial ratio calculated by dividing net credit sales by average trade receivables, which indicates how efficiently a company collects its outstanding debts. It offers insight into a firm's liquidity and operational efficiency. Effective receivables management has a direct positive impact on cash flow, working capital utilization, and overall profitability. An increase in the receivables turnover ratio is typically associated with a higher gross profit margin,

suggesting that firms with faster collection cycles tend to demonstrate stronger operational performance (Lee, 2023).

Operating Margin (C5) – This criterion is a key profitability metric that measures the proportion of revenue remaining after deducting operating expenses. It represents the ratio of operating income to total revenue and serves as a fundamental indicator of a firm's operational efficiency. Due to its focus on core business activities, operating margin is widely used in the financial analysis and performance evaluation of companies across sectors (D'Ecclesia et al., 2024; Jin & Nembhard, 2022).

Cost of Goods Sold (C6) – COGS covers the costs of materials used and direct labor costs in producing a good. It also includes indirect and overhead expenses, such as distribution costs and sales service costs. A change is described as the direct circulation attributable to the production of the goods sold (Lukic et al., 2020; Moheb-Alizadeh & Handfield, 2018).

Market Capitalization (C7) – Market capitalization, a key indicator of a company's size, represents the value of a publicly traded company on the stock exchange. A company's current financial situation reflects its price and total outstanding shares. It is the total market value of a company's outstanding shares. It is calculated by multiplying the current market price of one share of a company's outstanding shares. Market capitalization, which provides information about how much investors are willing to pay for a company's shares, also provides investors with information about the company's characteristics and whether they should invest in it (Kumar & Kumara, 2021; Moussa et al., 2024).

Enterprise Value (C8) – This indicator include the current and potential benefits a business can generate. There are many different methodologies and approaches to calculating business value, which can be calculated and determined using different methods and appropriate pricing models(Dang et al., 2019; Yang et al., 2020). This value includes its assets, financial structure, earnings, and the impact of the environment in which it operates. The resulting this value not only serves the company's internal needs but is also a significant indicator for all stakeholders interested in being a part of the business(Jankalová et al., 2024).

4.1.2 Identification of the Alternatives

The codes and notations for the BIST Sustainability Index companies evaluated in this study are presented in Table 2. These companies constitute the alternatives in the initial decision matrix. The study analyzes the financial performance of BIST-listed firms from various sectors over the period 2021–2023.

Table 2: Companies listed in BIST

	Code	Companies
A1	AEFES	Anadolu Efes Brewery and Malt Industry Inc.
A2	AGHOL	Anadolu Group Holding Inc.
A3	AKSA	Aksa Acrylic Chemical Industry Inc.
A4	AKSEN	Aksa Energy Inc.
A5	ARCLK	ARÇELİK Inc.
A6	ASELS	Aselsan Inc.
A7	AYGAZ	Aygaz Inc.
A8	BIMAS	BİM Birleşik Mağazalar Inc.
A9	BRISA	Brisa Bridgestone Sabanci Tire Manufacturing Inc.

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Table 2: Companies listed in BIST (Cont...)

Code	Companies
A10	CCOLA
A11	CİMSA
A12	DOAS
A13	DOHOL
A14	ENJSA
A15	ENKAI
A16	EREGL
A17	FROTO
A18	KCHOL
A19	LOGO
A20	MGROS
A21	PGSUS
A22	SAHOL
A23	SISE
A24	SOKM
A25	TAVHL
A26	TCELL
A27	THYAO
A28	TKFEN
A29	TOASO
A30	TTKOM
A31	TTRAK
A32	TUPRS
A33	ULKER
A34	VESBE
A35	VESTL
A36	ZOREN

4.2 Evaluating financial performance using the SITDE-RAWEC Hybrid Model

The steps outlined in the SITDE-RAWEC hybrid method algorithm have been sequentially applied to determine and rank the alternatives as follows. Although the financial data covers the years 2021, 2022, and 2023, the complete implementation of all methodological steps was conducted using the data from 2023.

For 2023:

Stage 1: Calculating the weights of the criteria with the SITDE method.

Step 1-1: The decision matrix for 2023 is shown in Table A.1.

Step 1-2: The normalized decision matrix obtained by Eq. (2) is shown in Table A.2. For example, for first criteria and first alternative;

$$N_{11} = \frac{3.68}{-11.88} = -3.2294$$

Step 1-3: The skewness matrix obtained with Eq. (3) is shown in Table A.3. For example, for first criteria;

$$S_1 = \left(\frac{36}{(36-1) * (36-2)} \right) * \left(\frac{((-3.2294 - (-1.9139))^2 + (-4.7690 - (-1.9139))^2 + (-0.5886 - (-1.9139))^2 + \dots + (-1.1103 - (-1.9139))^2 + (-6.1351 - (-1.9139))^2)}{1.5306} \right)$$

$$= -1.2129$$

Step 1-4: The normalized skewness matrix obtained with Eq. (4) is shown in Table A.4. For example, for first criteria;

$$S_1^N = \log \left| \left((-1.2129) + 1 \right) + (|-4.5096| + 1) \right| = 0.7240.$$

Step 1-5: The importance matrix of the criteria obtained by Eq. (5) is shown in Table A.5. For example, for first criteria;

$$w_1 = \frac{0.7240}{0.7240+0.3010+0.9826+0.9857+0.8596+0.3826+0.9620+0.4928} = 0.1272.$$

Stage 2: Ranking the alternatives through the RAWEC method.

Step 2-1: The decision matrix in Table 3 is also used as the first step of the RAWEC method.

Step 2-2: The normalized decision matrices obtained by Eq. (6 and 7) is shown in Table A.6. and 7. For example, for first criteria and first alternative;

$$N_{11}^{1st} = \frac{3.68}{97.59} = 0.0377$$

$$N_{11}^{2nd} = \frac{-11.88}{3.68} = -3.294$$

Steps 2-3 and 2-4: The values obtained by Eq. (8-10) and the performance rankings of the alternatives are shown in Table A.8. For example, for first alternative;

$$D_1^{1st} = 0.1277 * (1 - 0.0377) + 0.0529 * (1 - 0.4521) + 0.1727 * (1 - 0.2249) + \dots + 0.0866 * (1 - 0.4835) = 0.7830.$$

$$D_1^{2nd} = 0.1277 * (1 - (-3.2294)) + 0.0529 * (1 - (-0.1437)) + 0.1727 * (1 - 0.2634) + \dots + 0.0866 * (1 - (-0.9775)) = 1.4876.$$

$$R_1 = \frac{1.4876 - 0.7830}{1.4876 + 0.7830} = 0.3104.$$

For 2022:

The decision matrix for 2022 is shown in Table A.9. The importance level matrix of the criteria is shown in Table A.10. The matrix showing the performance of the alternatives is shown in Table A.11.

For 2021:

The decision matrix for 2022 is shown in Table A.12. The importance level matrix of the criteria is shown in Table A.13. The matrix showing the performance of the alternatives is shown in Table A.14.

5. Results and Implications

During 2021, the ranking of companies' financial performance is as follows: ZOREN (A36) > SAHOL (A22) > DOHOL (A13) > THYAO (A27) > DOAS (A12).....MGROS (A20) > TKFEN (A28) > LOGO (A19) > ULKER (A33) > PGSUS (A21). According to this ranking, Zorlu Energy Electricity Generation Inc., HACI ÖMER SABANCI Holding Inc., and DOĞAN Companies Group Holding Inc. are the

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companies with the best financial performance.

Fig. 2 shows the rankings of alternatives by 2021.

Figure 2: The rankings of alternatives by 2021

Upon examining the criteria weights, the impact rankings of criteria in the decision-making process are as follows: " ROCE (C2) > Accounts Receivable Turnover (C4) > Tobin Q (C3) > Enterprise Value (C8) > Operating Margin (C5) > Cost of Goods Sold (C6) > Market Capitalization (C7) > P/E (C1) > > According to this ranking, the accounts receivables turnover ratio criterion in 2021 is considered the most important criterion in assessing financial performance. The criterion with the lowest impact level in financial performance calculation is the ROCE.

Fig. 3 shows the rankings of alternatives by 2022.

Figure 3: The rankings of alternatives by 2022

During 2022, the ranking of companies' financial performance is as follows: AYGAZ (A7) > SOKM (A24) > ENJSA (A14) > AGHOL (A2) > TUPRS (A32) ENKAI (A15) > ASELS (A6) > VESBE (A34) > ZOREN (A36) > VESTL (A35). According to this ranking, Aygaz Inc., Enerjisa Energy Inc., and Anadolu Group Holding Inc. are the

companies with the best financial performance.

Upon examining the criteria weights, the impact rankings of criteria in the decision-making process are as follows: "Enterprise Value (C8) > Tobin Q (C3) > Accounts Receivable Turnover (C4) > ROCE (C2) > Market Capitalization (C7) > Operating Margin (C5) > P/E (C1) > Cost of Goods Sold (C6)". According to this ranking, the Enterprise Value criterion in 2022 is considered the most important criterion in assessing financial performance. The criterion with the lowest impact level in financial performance calculation is the Cost of Goods Sold.

Fig. 4 shows the rankings of alternatives by 2023.

Figure 4: The rankings of alternatives by 2023

During 2023, the ranking of companies' financial performance is as follows: AYGAZ (A7) > LOGO (A19) > THYAO (A27) > KCHOL (A18) > FROTO (A17)TCELL (A26) > ENJSA (A14) > VESTL (A35) > SAHOL (A22) > SOKM (A24). According to this ranking, Aygaz Inc., Logo Software Inc., and Turkish Airlines Inc. are the companies with the best financial performance.

Upon examining the criteria weights, the impact rankings of criteria in the decision-making process are as follows: "Accounts Receivable Turnover (C4) > Tobin Q (C3) > Market Capitalization (C7) > Operating Margin (C5) > P/E (C1) > Enterprise Value (C8) > Cost of Goods Sold (C6) > ROCE (C2). According to this ranking, the Receivables turnover ratio criterion in 2023 is considered the most important criterion in assessing financial performance. The criterion with the lowest impact level in financial performance calculation is the ROCE.

5.1 Comparative Performance Analysis (2021–2023)

A three-year evaluation revealed significant fluctuations in the performance rankings of the 36 companies included in the Borsa Istanbul Sustainability Index. Compared to 2021, 20 companies experienced a decline in performance in 2023, while 16 saw an increase. The company that showed the most significant improvement was Zorlu Enerji (A36). Ranking 35th in 2021, the company made the largest jump to first place in 2023. Similarly, Sabancı Holding (A22) made significant progress, moving from 6th place in 2021 to 2nd place in 2023.

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In contrast, the company that experienced the most significant decline was Pegasus (A21). Pegasus, which ranked 18th in 2021, exhibited the weakest performance, falling to 36th in 2023. Logo Yazılım (A19) similarly experienced a significant performance decline, falling from 2nd place in 2022 to 34th in 2023. For companies in the middle ranks, fluctuations were relatively more limited. For example, Ereğli Demir Çelik (A16) rose from 21st place in 2021 to 9th in 2023, while Ford Otosan (A17) displayed a more consistent performance, remaining in 12th place in 2023 from 14th place in 2021. In conclusion, the analyzed period witnessed significant performance fluctuations and dramatic declines across companies. This finding demonstrates that global economic conditions, industry dynamics, and companies' strategic management practices are decisive factors in performance.

Fig. 5 shows the rankings of alternatives by year.

Figure 5: The rankings of alternatives by year

5.2 Research Implications

This study provides valuable theoretical, methodological, and practical insights for both academia and industry. The implications of the research are outlined as follows:

This study enriches the growing body of financial performance research by employing a multi-year, multi-sectoral dataset covering 36 companies listed on BIST across the 2021–2023 period. Through the use of eight financial criteria (including profitability, liquidity, capital efficiency, and market valuation) the research offers a comprehensive and replicable approach to measuring firm performance. The findings help clarify how financial structures vary across sectors and time, offering a foundation for future longitudinal studies.

The use of the SITDE and RAWEC methods represents a novel combination in the context of financial performance evaluation. By integrating objective weight determination and robust ranking, the study introduces a transparent, balanced, and repeatable approach for financial decision modeling. This methodological contribution is particularly valuable for researchers seeking replicable techniques in complex decision environments.

The ranking of firms based on aggregated performance scores provides investors with clear, data-driven insights into company resilience and efficiency over time. The ability to evaluate companies' relative standings across multiple criteria enables more informed portfolio decisions and risk assessments.

This study provides crucial information for all company stakeholders regarding

financial decision-making. It allows managers to understand which criteria are most important for financial recovery and sustainability after a significant crisis like the COVID-19 pandemic. Managers can take the necessary precautions based on the importance of each criterion in their company's planning processes. By comparing and analyzing their rankings with competitors, they can better align their financial strategies with current market expectations. Investors can make sound and strategic decisions based on the results of this study.

5.3 Comparative Analyses

For example, comparative analyses were performed based on data from only 2022 and 2023. In the comparative analysis, the RAWEC method was compared with the MARCOS ([Stanković et al., 2020](#)) and CORASO ([Puška et al., 2024](#)) methods. The results of the comparative analysis are shown in A.15.

6. Discussion

This research used the SITDE-RAWEC hybrid method for determine 2021-2023 term performance of 36 companies included in the sustainability index in Türkiye.

The important findings one of the research are determined weights of financial performance indicators. SITDE method using for this determined the criteria weights. This study show that ROCE (C2) is the important indicator affecting financial performance in 2021. Enterprise Value (C8) is the important indicator affecting financial performance in 2022. Accounts Receivable Turnover (C4) is the important indicator affecting financial performance in 2023. This finding is similar to the results of the study by ([Katrancı et al., 2025](#)). [Katrancı et al. \(2025\)](#) found that the Accounts Receivable Turnover ratio was the most significant criterion influencing financial performance.

Research have shown that financial performance varies depending on the sector, country dynamics, selected financial criteria, index, selected companies, period and method examined ([Çalikoğlu & Łuczak, 2024](#)).

7. Conclusion

Performance assessment was based on eight financial indicators capturing market value, profitability, liquidity, and efficiency. The RAWEC method was used to rank companies according to their overall performance, while criterion weights were objectively determined through the SITDE approach. This integrated design enabled a transparent and equitable evaluation of firms across multiple years and financial dimensions.

The results indicated notable disparities in financial performance. Zorlu Energy (ZOREN) recorded the highest score, followed by Sabancı Holding (SAHOL) and Doğan Holding (DOHOL). In contrast, Pegasus Airlines (PGSUS) and Ülker Biscuit (ULKER) were positioned at the lower end of the ranking in terms of financial strength. These outcomes provide meaningful insights for stakeholders aiming to assess firms' resilience, particularly against the backdrop of post-pandemic economic volatility.

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The use of the SITDE–RAWEC framework illustrates the practical utility of hybrid MCDM methods in financial performance analysis. By integrating objective weighting with entropy-based ranking, the study offers a replicable and adaptable decision-support model that can guide investors, corporate managers, and policymakers in benchmarking, portfolio optimization, and strategic planning.

8. Study Limitations

The research examined companies (excluding banks and insurance companies) traded in the BIST sustainability index included in the sustainability index in 2021, 2022, and 2023; data were limited to these years. The decision matrix includes eight financial and stock market indicator. SITDE determined criterion weights, and RAWEC were used for performance ranking.

9. Future Research Directions

Although the study offers valuable contributions, it is not without certain limitations. To begin with, the analysis is confined to a sample of 36 companies listed on BIST, which may not adequately capture the diversity of all industries or reflect patterns in other emerging and developed markets. Additionally, the three-year observation period may be insufficient to account for long-term cyclical movements or structural transformations in financial performance. Furthermore, while the use of eight financial ratios provides a multidimensional foundation, the framework does not include non-financial factors such as ESG ratings, governance practices, or macroeconomic disruptions, which could further enhance explanatory depth.

Future studies may broaden the analysis by incorporating firms from different stock exchanges or industry-focused indices, and by adding qualitative dimensions such as strategic management approaches, digital transformation initiatives, or sustainability reporting. Moreover, the integration of advanced tools such as fuzzy logic, machine learning techniques, or dynamic time-series–based MCDM models could improve the robustness and predictive accuracy of financial performance assessments. Examining the interaction between financial outcomes and external shocks, including regulatory reforms, interest rate fluctuations, or global crises, may also provide a deeper understanding of financial sustainability at the firm level.

Future studies can include banks and insurance companies in the alternatives. Researchers can also analyze the performance of firms over even longer terms such as last ten years. Future research can implement more financial and non financial indicators, ratios, stock market indicators and ESG score (environmental, social, and governance). Researchers can also analyze different index and different sector.

Future research can also employ alternative MCDM techniques (e.g., VIKOR, DEMATEL, SAW) and a different approach (entropy, BWM) to find the criterion weights.

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Appendix

Table A.1: The initial decision matrix

	C1	C2	C3	C4	C5	C6	C7	C8
A1	3.68	34.28	0.53	100877.00	12.55	12.24	81414.40	165224.30
A2	2.49	33.18	0.34	276294.88	22.56	4.70	48926.18	184861.53
A3	20.19	14.70	1.48	19979.70	30.14	10.94	33346.30	33496.70
A4	6.64	22.46	0.89	27956.90	3.96	19.27	36471.30	51143.70
A5	11.32	12.27	0.54	181725.70	3.55	3.95	86831.00	167490.60
A6	28.13	7.35	1.14	53487.60	4.92	33.93	205108.80	216627.60
A7	4.98	17.83	0.69	59871.90	17.21	0.33	29673.10	26057.60
A8	11.83	20.36	1.06	276759.30	19.57	1.21	182615.40	204325.00
A9	5.91	32.02	1.06	19999.20	7.49	7.69	23570.30	24803.30
A10	6.50	51.40	1.55	68002.60	16.25	14.33	133672.00	154249.30
A11	11.14	20.52	0.95	16475.18	12.12	16.41	27743.64	34870.37
A12	2.88	47.39	0.83	117114.93	45.50	17.84	56540.00	59515.31
A13	97.59	0.86	0.55	42981.60	10.03	21.89	28944.00	21629.20
A14	11.91	7.75	0.67	143110.20	13.64	8.83	53785.90	77585.70
A15	12.02	10.08	0.75	60828.30	9.27	16.90	204000.00	121116.20
A16	34.14	2.67	0.68	133658.00	8.55	9.02	143500.00	190605.30
A17	5.29	65.26	1.67	356657.70	20.87	10.69	259497.90	341734.70
A18	4.98	15.78	0.25	995950.00	8.30	18.27	359463.00	251001.00
A19	52.76	8.76	1.45	550.58	4.96	9.89	7395.00	6777.67
A20	6.87	24.40	0.57	147671.40	280.70	3.64	60653.09	56320.41
A21	3.18	57.51	0.92	53713.13	49.60	18.56	66443.66	151348.91
A22	8.00	5.96	0.14	115931.17	11.49	90.81	123342.42	-161507.17
A23	8.20	10.69	0.68	110055.80	4.56	10.34	140356.47	220405.22
A24	7.20	22.54	0.72	106807.11	9799.43	-0.95	32008.00	34106.41
A25	5.19	21.78	0.63	21143.43	11.50	18.88	39052.71	74314.49
A26	9.83	9.12	0.84	84418.04	10.49	22.03	123420.00	155741.73
A27	1.94	47.60	0.37	384952.00	23.03	14.16	315468.03	209477.56
A28	-11.88	-4.93	0.43	41907.03	3.71	-8.46	13660.40	13660.40
A29	6.96	39.72	1.13	105107.91	8.29	10.98	105000.00	87358.96
A30	5.19	15.32	0.57	78315.94	6.49	4.85	85260.00	145426.10
A31	7.63	75.82	2.37	42844.38	31.68	19.35	71247.62	64685.69
A32	5.14	23.78	0.65	576796.12	18.04	10.72	275531.83	192834.71
A33	8.95	20.66	0.92	39659.58	9.66	19.69	30225.24	54080.61
A34	5.42	26.89	0.59	51094.96	4.48	4.41	25600.00	25600.00
A35	10.70	4.57	0.36	87243.11	6.34	-6.86	15511.49	47385.00
A36	1.94	38.93	0.65	23519.57	5.09	12.00	21150.00	61379.84

Table A.2: The normalized decision matrix

	C1	C2	C3	C4	C5	C6	C7	C8
A1	-3.2294	-0.1437	0.2634	0.1013	0.2829	-0.6910	0.0908	-0.9775
A2	-4.7690	-0.1485	0.4099	0.2774	0.1574	-1.8009	0.1511	-0.8737
A3	-0.5886	-0.3352	0.0951	0.0201	0.1178	-0.7727	0.2218	-4.8216
A4	-1.7906	-0.2194	0.1572	0.0281	0.8965	-0.4387	0.2028	-3.1579
A5	-1.0491	-0.4015	0.2612	0.1825	1.0000	-2.1404	0.0852	-0.9643
A6	-0.4223	-0.6703	0.1238	0.0537	0.7220	-0.2492	0.0361	-0.7456
A7	-2.3839	-0.2763	0.2036	0.0601	0.2062	-25.9351	0.2492	-6.1981
A8	-1.0046	-0.2420	0.1328	0.2779	0.1814	-7.0136	0.0405	-0.7904
A9	-2.0090	-0.1539	0.1330	0.0201	0.4738	-1.0992	0.3137	-6.5115
A10	-1.8292	-0.0959	0.0907	0.0683	0.2184	-0.5903	0.0553	-1.0471
A11	-1.0667	-0.2401	0.1483	0.0165	0.2928	-0.5153	0.2665	-4.6316

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Table A.2: The normalized decision matrix (continued)

	C1	C2	C3	C4	C5	C6	C7	C8
A12	-4.1233	-0.1040	0.1700	0.1176	0.0780	-0.4739	0.1308	-2.7137
A13	-0.1218	-5.7290	0.2575	0.0432	0.3539	-0.3864	0.2555	-7.4671
A14	-0.9979	-0.6357	0.2109	0.1437	0.2603	-0.9575	0.1375	-2.0817
A15	-0.9883	-0.4888	0.1875	0.0611	0.3829	-0.5005	0.0363	-1.3335
A16	-0.3480	-1.8453	0.2063	0.1342	0.4153	-0.9379	0.0515	-0.8473
A17	-2.2460	-0.0755	0.0842	0.3581	0.1701	-0.7913	0.0285	-0.4726
A18	-2.3874	-0.3123	0.5639	1.0000	0.4276	-0.4630	0.0206	-0.6435
A19	-0.2252	-0.5625	0.0970	0.0006	0.7159	-0.8549	1.0000	-23.8293
A20	-1.7294	-0.2019	0.2481	0.1483	0.0126	-2.3242	0.1219	-2.8676
A21	-3.7386	-0.0857	0.1527	0.0539	0.0716	-0.4557	0.1113	-1.0671
A22	-1.4861	-0.8267	1.0000	0.1164	0.3091	-0.0931	0.0600	1.0000
A23	-1.4493	-0.4609	0.2070	0.1105	0.7783	-0.8177	0.0527	-0.7328
A24	-1.6504	-0.2186	0.1947	0.1072	0.0004	8.8695	0.2310	-4.7354
A25	-2.2909	-0.2262	0.2238	0.0212	0.3088	-0.4478	0.1894	-2.1733
A26	-1.2085	-0.5405	0.1674	0.0848	0.3385	-0.3839	0.0599	-1.0370
A27	-6.1388	-0.1035	0.3824	0.3865	0.1542	-0.5972	0.0234	-0.7710
A28	1.0000	1.0000	0.3246	0.0421	0.9568	1.0000	0.5413	-11.8230
A29	-1.7067	-0.1240	0.1241	0.1055	0.4280	-0.7703	0.0704	-1.8488
A30	-2.2884	-0.3215	0.2460	0.0786	0.5468	-1.7438	0.0867	-1.1106
A31	-1.5578	-0.0650	0.0592	0.0430	0.1120	-0.4370	0.1038	-2.4968
A32	-2.3103	-0.2072	0.2165	0.5791	0.1968	-0.7885	0.0268	-0.8375
A33	-1.3282	-0.2385	0.1523	0.0398	0.3673	-0.4295	0.2447	-2.9864
A34	-2.1926	-0.1833	0.2371	0.0513	0.7922	-1.9185	0.2889	-6.3089
A35	-1.1103	-1.0777	0.3894	0.0876	0.5597	1.2331	0.4767	-3.4084
A36	-6.1351	-0.1265	0.2176	0.0236	0.6973	-0.7048	0.3496	-2.6313

Table A.3: The skewness matrix

	C1	C2	C3	C4	C5	C6	C7	C8
S_j	-1.2129	-4.5096	3.0967	3.1656	0.7278	-4.0961	2.6525	-3.3991

Table A.4: The normalized skewness matrix

	C1	C2	C3	C4	C5	C6	C7	C8
S_j^N	0.7240	0.3010	0.9826	0.9857	0.8596	0.3826	0.9620	0.4928

Table A.5: The importance of the criteria

	C1	C2	C3	C4	C5	C6	C7	C8
w_j	0.1272	0.0529	0.1727	0.1732	0.1511	0.0672	0.1691	0.0866
Ranking	5	8	2	1	4	7	3	6

Table A.6: The normalized decision matrix N^{1st}_{ij}

	C1	C2	C3	C4	C5	C6	C7	C8
A1	0.0377	0.4521	0.2249	0.1013	0.2829	0.1348	0.2265	0.4835
A2	0.0255	0.4376	0.1445	0.2774	0.1574	0.0517	0.1361	0.5410
A3	0.2068	0.1939	0.6226	0.0201	0.1178	0.1205	0.0928	0.0980
A4	0.0680	0.2962	0.3768	0.0281	0.8965	0.2122	0.1015	0.1497
A5	0.1160	0.1618	0.2267	0.1825	1.0000	0.0435	0.2416	0.4901
A6	0.2883	0.0969	0.4782	0.0537	0.7220	0.3737	0.5706	0.6339
A7	0.0511	0.2352	0.2909	0.0601	0.2062	0.0036	0.0825	0.0763
A8	0.1212	0.2685	0.4458	0.2779	0.1814	0.0133	0.5080	0.5979
A9	0.0606	0.4223	0.4454	0.0201	0.4738	0.0847	0.0656	0.0726
A10	0.0666	0.6779	0.6529	0.0683	0.2184	0.1577	0.3719	0.4514
A11	0.1141	0.2706	0.3994	0.0165	0.2928	0.1807	0.0772	0.1020
A12	0.0295	0.6250	0.3483	0.1176	0.0780	0.1965	0.1573	0.1742
A13	1.0000	0.0113	0.2300	0.0432	0.3539	0.2410	0.0805	0.0633
A14	0.1220	0.1022	0.2808	0.1437	0.2603	0.0973	0.1496	0.2270
A15	0.1232	0.1329	0.3158	0.0611	0.3829	0.1861	0.5675	0.3544
A16	0.3499	0.0352	0.2871	0.1342	0.4153	0.0993	0.3992	0.5578
A17	0.0542	0.8607	0.7036	0.3581	0.1701	0.1177	0.7219	1.0000
A18	0.0510	0.2081	0.1050	1.0000	0.4276	0.2011	1.0000	0.7345
A19	0.5407	0.1155	0.6107	0.0006	0.7159	0.1089	0.0206	0.0198
A20	0.0704	0.3218	0.2387	0.1483	0.0126	0.0401	0.1687	0.1648
A21	0.0326	0.7585	0.3879	0.0539	0.0716	0.2043	0.1848	0.4429
A22	0.0819	0.0786	0.0592	0.1164	0.3091	1.0000	0.3431	-0.4726
A23	0.0840	0.1410	0.2862	0.1105	0.7783	0.1139	0.3905	0.6450
A24	0.0738	0.2973	0.3042	0.1072	0.0004	-0.0105	0.0890	0.0998
A25	0.0531	0.2873	0.2647	0.0212	0.3088	0.2079	0.1086	0.2175
A26	0.1007	0.1202	0.3538	0.0848	0.3385	0.2426	0.3433	0.4557
A27	0.0198	0.6278	0.1549	0.3865	0.1542	0.1559	0.8776	0.6130
A28	-0.1218	-0.0650	0.1824	0.0421	0.9568	-0.0931	0.0380	0.0400
A29	0.0713	0.5238	0.4773	0.1055	0.4280	0.1209	0.2921	0.2556
A30	0.0532	0.2021	0.2407	0.0786	0.5468	0.0534	0.2372	0.4256
A31	0.0782	1.0000	1.0000	0.0430	0.1120	0.2131	0.1982	0.1893
A32	0.0527	0.3136	0.2735	0.5791	0.1968	0.1181	0.7665	0.5643
A33	0.0917	0.2724	0.3888	0.0398	0.3673	0.2168	0.0841	0.1583
A34	0.0555	0.3546	0.2498	0.0513	0.7922	0.0485	0.0712	0.0749
A35	0.1097	0.0603	0.1521	0.0876	0.5597	-0.0755	0.0432	0.1387
A36	0.0198	0.5135	0.2722	0.0236	0.6973	0.1321	0.0588	0.1796

Table A.7: The normalized decision matrix N^{2nd}_{ij}

	C1	C2	C3	C4	C5	C6	C7	C8
A1	-3.2294	-0.1437	0.2634	0.0055	0.0013	-0.6910	0.0908	-0.9775
A2	-4.7690	-0.1485	0.4099	0.0020	0.0023	-1.8009	0.1511	-0.8737
A3	-0.5886	-0.3352	0.0951	0.0276	0.0031	-0.7727	0.2218	-4.8216
A4	-1.7906	-0.2194	0.1572	0.0197	0.0004	-0.4387	0.2028	-3.1579
A5	-1.0491	-0.4015	0.2612	0.0030	0.0004	-2.1404	0.0852	-0.9643
A6	-0.4223	-0.6703	0.1238	0.0103	0.0005	-0.2492	0.0361	-0.7456
A7	-2.3839	-0.2763	0.2036	0.0092	0.0018	-25.9351	0.2492	-6.1981
A8	-1.0046	-0.2420	0.1328	0.0020	0.0020	-7.0136	0.0405	-0.7904
A9	-2.0090	-0.1539	0.1330	0.0275	0.0008	-1.0992	0.3137	-6.5115

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Table A.7: The normalized decision matrix N^{2nd}_{ij} (continued)

	C1	C2	C3	C4	C5	C6	C7	C8
A10	-1.8292	-0.0959	0.0907	0.0081	0.0017	-0.5903	0.0553	-1.0471
A11	-1.0667	-0.2401	0.1483	0.0334	0.0012	-0.5153	0.2665	-4.6316
A12	-4.1233	-0.1040	0.1700	0.0047	0.0046	-0.4739	0.1308	-2.7137
A13	-0.1218	-5.7290	0.2575	0.0128	0.0010	-0.3864	0.2555	-7.4671
A14	-0.9979	-0.6357	0.2109	0.0038	0.0014	-0.9575	0.1375	-2.0817
A15	-0.9883	-0.4888	0.1875	0.0091	0.0009	-0.5005	0.0363	-1.3335
A16	-0.3480	-1.8453	0.2063	0.0041	0.0009	-0.9379	0.0515	-0.8473
A17	-2.2460	-0.0755	0.0842	0.0015	0.0021	-0.7913	0.0285	-0.4726
A18	-2.3874	-0.3123	0.5639	0.0006	0.0008	-0.4630	0.0206	-0.6435
A19	-0.2252	-0.5625	0.0970	1.0000	0.0005	-0.8549	1.0000	-23.8293
A20	-1.7294	-0.2019	0.2481	0.0037	0.0286	-2.3242	0.1219	-2.8676
A21	-3.7386	-0.0857	0.1527	0.0103	0.0051	-0.4557	0.1113	-1.0671
A22	-1.4861	-0.8267	1.0000	0.0047	0.0012	-0.0931	0.0600	1.0000
A23	-1.4493	-0.4609	0.2070	0.0050	0.0005	-0.8177	0.0527	-0.7328
A24	-1.6504	-0.2186	0.1947	0.0052	1.0000	8.8695	0.2310	-4.7354
A25	-2.2909	-0.2262	0.2238	0.0260	0.0012	-0.4478	0.1894	-2.1733
A26	-1.2085	-0.5405	0.1674	0.0065	0.0011	-0.3839	0.0599	-1.0370
A27	-6.1388	-0.1035	0.3824	0.0014	0.0023	-0.5972	0.0234	-0.7710
A28	1.0000	1.0000	0.3246	0.0131	0.0004	1.0000	0.5413	-11.8230
A29	-1.7067	-0.1240	0.1241	0.0052	0.0008	-0.7703	0.0704	-1.8488
A30	-2.2884	-0.3215	0.2460	0.0070	0.0007	-1.7438	0.0867	-1.1106
A31	-1.5578	-0.0650	0.0592	0.0129	0.0032	-0.4370	0.1038	-2.4968
A32	-2.3103	-0.2072	0.2165	0.0010	0.0018	-0.7885	0.0268	-0.8375
A33	-1.3282	-0.2385	0.1523	0.0139	0.0010	-0.4295	0.2447	-2.9864
A34	-2.1926	-0.1833	0.2371	0.0108	0.0005	-1.9185	0.2889	-6.3089
A35	-1.1103	-1.0777	0.3894	0.0063	0.0006	1.2331	0.4767	-3.4084
A36	-6.1351	-0.1265	0.2176	0.0234	0.0005	-0.7048	0.3496	-2.6313

Table A.8: D^{1st}_i , D^{2nd}_i and R_i values and alternatives' rankings

Alt.	D^{1st}_i	D^{2nd}_i	R_i	Ranking	Alt.	D^{1st}_i	D^{2nd}_i	R_i	Ranking
A1	0.7830	1.4876	0.3104	24	A19	0.6989	2.8206	0.6028	2
A2	0.8035	1.7144	0.3618	13	A20	0.8597	1.5670	0.2914	27
A3	0.8024	1.5030	0.3039	25	A21	0.7852	1.5556	0.3291	16
A4	0.7259	1.4775	0.3411	15	A22	0.8240	0.9687	0.0807	35
A5	0.6686	1.3221	0.3282	17	A23	0.6662	1.2817	0.3160	22
A6	0.5808	1.1412	0.3255	18	A24	0.8807	0.8106	-0.0415	36
A7	0.8685	3.5196	0.6042	1	A25	0.8308	1.4464	0.2703	31
A8	0.6793	1.6503	0.4168	8	A26	0.7401	1.2577	0.2591	32
A9	0.7949	1.8207	0.3922	10	A27	0.6353	1.8229	0.4831	3
A10	0.6855	1.3415	0.3236	19	A28	0.8320	1.6267	0.3232	20
A11	0.8211	1.5076	0.2948	26	A29	0.7182	1.4013	0.3223	21
A12	0.8160	1.7440	0.3625	12	A30	0.7642	1.4632	0.3138	23
A13	0.7362	1.9012	0.4417	6	A31	0.6759	1.4168	0.3541	14
A14	0.8149	1.3447	0.2454	33	A32	0.6130	1.3881	0.3873	11
A15	0.7152	1.2605	0.2760	29	A33	0.8019	1.3989	0.2713	30
A16	0.6956	1.2332	0.2787	28	A34	0.7807	1.8724	0.4115	9
A17	0.5218	1.3640	0.4466	5	A35	0.8427	1.2615	0.1991	34
A18	0.4804	1.3061	0.4622	4	A36	0.7795	1.9618	0.4313	7

Table A.9: The initial decision matrix

	C1	C2	C3	C4	C5	C6	C7	C8
A1	2.61	36.96	0.38	101504.40	19.06	11.08	40115.10	131336.20
A2	1.72	49.69	0.31	236681.50	30.63	4.43	26886.30	169501.40
A3	8.70	79.82	2.82	13162.70	23.80	20.40	29768.80	30473.10
A4	12.64	33.97	1.99	40190.40	8.05	11.77	57637.90	66752.70
A5	12.06	17.42	0.69	188501.50	6.56	3.66	75816.70	125262.30
A6	110.58	2.43	1.10	49026.90	6.76	26.86	141764.20	144126.90
A7	3.07	41.13	0.59	67429.70	29.62	-0.04	21013.00	21478.80
A8	5.01	50.79	0.81	237.18	36.19	2.08	83125.70	96399.70
A9	7.24	36.27	0.90	20909.00	11.88	5.48	18154.50	21449.80
A10	3.75	51.54	0.80	64.71	28.91	12.31	51993.40	68356.50
A11	3.95	83.60	1.41	7102.60	11.78	15.14	13562.50	14144.00
A12	5.51	87.70	1.01	36255.30	56.56	16.94	43120.00	41738.70
A13	4.60	36.32	0.94	40282.20	13.28	15.17	27687.20	25078.10
A14	1.24	60.52	0.46	140112.60	22.00	10.88	25570.60	38708.60
A15	101.38	1.87	1.26	47506.80	12.97	19.82	198840.00	156933.90
A16	8.02	18.19	0.99	102244.10	9.81	18.45	144410.00	160993.30
A17	6.64	90.49	1.41	685957.50	42.03	8.45	184052.30	229865.20
A18	3.21	33.84	0.30	609386.00	9.30	20.35	223897.50	586440.50
A19	16.78	44.95	2.71	262.60	4.29	24.35	6957.00	6359.10
A20	2.90	65.35	0.48	114210.30	290.27	3.43	26524.40	24596.50
A21	6.92	57.00	1.15	31155.50	56.52	22.64	49103.90	97284.20
A22	2.33	29.28	0.15	105388.50	16.35	137.97	91981.40	291938.20
A23	5.78	24.91	0.72	116072.70	8.17	14.59	131473.10	190196.30
A24	2.39	75.79	0.51	89633.30	4316.31	0.03	16588.40	22218.30
A25	17.89	9.95	0.73	10603.10	10.29	21.60	33966.80	54035.10
A26	12.11	10.43	0.73	81680.90	9.63	18.84	83336.00	117677.90
A27	4.10	32.87	0.44	235528.00	20.11	15.69	194442.90	167718.80
A28	13.12	8.53	0.42	52197.30	6.35	0.49	18226.20	18226.20
A29	9.68	59.34	1.28	53536.70	14.84	13.62	82850.00	74668.00
A30	20.79	14.54	0.83	29577.40	4.78	19.36	85960.00	138474.50
A31	8.17	76.31	1.60	34948.70	41.54	8.80	35223.50	33663.60
A32	2.38	62.34	0.58	803671.30	43.56	8.32	145858.70	120066.60
A33	15.18	13.11	0.77	40653.00	13.71	13.58	14952.20	39012.00
A34	104.10	2.30	0.71	53782.10	8.64	2.44	22048.00	22048.00
A35	-214.68	-0.60	0.53	92235.30	9.01	-7.08	23901.20	59015.50
A36	159.61	0.93	0.77	26171.20	6.97	13.93	17757.00	49135.70

Table A.10: The importance of the criteria

	C1	C2	C3	C4	C5	C6	C7	C8
w_j	0.0643	0.1488	0.1535	0.1525	0.1234	0.0569	0.1437	0.1569
Ranking	7	4	2	3	6	8	5	1

Table A.11: The alternatives' rankings

Alt.	R_i	Ranking	Alt.	R_i	Ranking	Alt.	R_i	Ranking	Alt.	R_i	Ranking
A1	0.7582	8	A10	0.7507	9	A19	0.3249	29	A28	0.4727	24
A2	0.8291	4	A11	0.6994	12	A20	0.7465	10	A29	0.5193	23
A3	0.5762	19	A12	0.6421	15	A21	0.5850	18	A30	0.3006	31
A4	0.4462	25	A13	0.6388	16	A22	0.7994	6	A31	0.5594	20

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Table A.11: The alternatives' rankings (cont...)

<i>Alt.</i>	R_i	<i>Ranking</i>	<i>Alt.</i>	R_i	<i>Ranking</i>	<i>Alt.</i>	R_i	<i>Ranking</i>	<i>Alt.</i>	R_i	<i>Ranking</i>
A5	0.4240	26	A14	0.8688	3	A23	0.6182	17	A32	0.8006	5
A6	0.1682	33	A15	0.2267	32	A24	0.9319	2	A33	0.3257	28
A7	1.4566	1	A16	0.5486	21	A25	0.3036	30	A34	0.1217	34
A8	0.6773	13	A17	0.6688	14	A26	0.4158	27	A35	-0.3025	36
A9	0.5277	22	A18	0.7828	7	A27	0.7029	11	A36	0.0863	35

Table A.12: The initial decision matrix

	C1	C2	C3	C4	C5	C6	C7	C8
A1	16.42	6.78	0.45	25142.10	11.12	11.16	175388.20	49129.10
A2	7.42	17.50	1.04	57089.70	17.35	6.38	9575.80	58381.60
A3	9.51	49.66	1.49	6504.30	15.01	14.93	11098.20	11237.40
A4	7.29	24.22	0.87	11808.80	3.99	14.83	12251.10	17728.10
A5	10.67	18.46	0.77	48706.10	3.88	10.30	32705.20	50931.30
A6	6.68	32.83	1.14	13490.00	4.37	46.77	47606.40	48656.70
A7	10.05	26.72	1.11	14455.10	20.26	2.63	6732.00	7150.50
A8	12.69	39.68	1.49	57.24	22.13	5.83	37221.40	42578.20
A9	8.84	53.61	1.33	4618.30	8.50	9.70	8878.90	10190.20
A10	9.92	21.93	0.96	14.21	18.01	15.66	22524.60	29614.90
A11	4.09	49.89	1.05	3032.40	10.12	19.86	4160.60	5540.10
A12	4.13	70.26	1.30	20784.70	57.87	12.72	9636.00	9268.00
A13	2.54	26.50	0.53	14480.60	11.81	12.82	7196.60	3189.00
A14	6.67	27.66	0.85	24712.50	7.80	13.68	15212.20	22776.10
A15	16.35	7.47	0.71	19072.70	8.42	19.87	84336.00	30504.80
A16	6.35	25.43	0.91	42711.00	9.30	36.45	98560.00	94291.00
A17	9.49	102.38	2.40	59947.10	23.55	13.27	38551.70	88384.10
A18	4.74	27.63	0.35	227236.40	8.67	12.67	71968.80	204144.90
A19	15.73	41.96	2.45	142.70	2.70	27.62	4162.00	3911.80
A20	19.14	126.56	0.72	27517.70	208.34	2.37	6869.20	9217.00
A21	-4.41	-32.19	0.86	10546.90	39.89	-5.74	8690.40	37814.10
A22	2.24	26.91	0.18	24024.80	10.02	82.94	26994.50	89625.10
A23	4.53	29.16	0.74	20877.60	4.75	20.10	40985.80	64637.90
A24	23.98	86.07	1.11	21767.70	520.46	3.41	7777.60	9439.30
A25	25.40	4.01	0.57	3249.10	5.60	11.00	11879.30	27447.10
A26	5.69	23.21	0.67	86138.10	15.30	13.26	40612.00	57329.70
A27	3.23	15.70	0.25	74172.80	11.21	13.23	27627.60	53798.70
A28	8.92	12.60	0.50	14942.90	5.42	-2.95	7488.80	7488.80
A29	11.54	64.26	1.94	24065.20	20.30	13.80	37850.00	41394.00
A30	5.85	34.83	1.09	19404.40	5.39	23.67	33705.00	55794.80
A31	9.04	75.72	2.14	9511.30	19.01	12.14	11954.70	11522.90
A32	12.16	23.10	0.71	136632.00	22.65	0.51	42499.70	54783.50
A33	-12.84	-10.29	0.92	8924.70	7.79	19.39	5961.10	16045.40
A34	8.30	36.79	0.98	13613.30	3.83	11.42	12608.80	12608.80
A35	4.43	22.96	0.48	23487.00	5.39	5.58	8399.80	19295.90
A36	-48.01	-1.97	0.79	9771.70	5.78	23.54	4150.00	26330.90

Table A.13: The importance of the criteria

	C1	C2	C3	C4	C5	C6	C7	C8
w_j	0.1207	0.1484	0.1425	0.1461	0.1300	0.0441	0.1298	0.1383
Ranking	7	1	3	2	5	8	6	4

Table A.14: The alternatives' rankings

Alt.	R_i	Ranking	Alt.	R_i	Ranking	Alt.	R_i	Ranking	Alt.	R_i	Ranking
A1	0.4656	10	A10	0.4390	14	A19	0,2274	34	A28	0.3025	33
A2	0.4029	20	A11	0.4571	11	A20	0,3188	32	A29	0.3777	24
A3	0.3406	27	A12	0.4977	5	A21	-4,6413	36	A30	0.4358	16
A4	0.3590	25	A13	0.5557	3	A22	0,6248	2	A31	0.3833	22
A5	0.3363	28	A14	0.3848	21	A23	0,4790	7	A32	0.4329	17
A6	0.4208	18	A15	0.4190	19	A24	0,3574	26	A33	-1.2223	35
A7	0.3281	30	A16	0.4668	9	A25	0,4761	8	A34	0.3267	31
A8	0.3781	23	A17	0.4570	12	A26	0,4361	15	A35	0.4444	13
A9	0.3362	29	A18	0.4954	6	A27	0,5334	4	A36	4.6371	1

Table A.15: Comparative analysis

2023						2022						
RAWEC		MARCOS		CORASO		RAWEC		MARCOS		CORASO		
Values	Ranking	Values	Ranking	Values	Ranking	Values	Ranking	Values	Ranking	Values	Ranking	
A1	0.5449	24	0.2040	16	0.6664	30	0.6030	8	0.5591	31	0.8217	31
A2	0.6246	13	0.2873	9	0.6656	34	0.6433	4	0.4479	34	0.8216	32
A3	0.5349	25	0.2267	13	0.7230	8	0.4995	19	0.7077	15	0.8588	9
A4	0.5925	15	0.1699	20	0.6851	14	0.4256	25	0.7278	11	0.8335	16
A5	0.5726	17	0.0920	32	0.6661	31	0.4130	26	0.7247	13	0.8219	30
A6	0.5683	18	0.0473	34	0.6958	10	0.2676	33	0.7665	4	0.8422	13
A7	1.0000	1	1.0000	1	0.9772	2	1.0000	1	1.0000	1	0.9880	2
A8	0.7098	8	0.2610	10	0.6792	20	0.5570	13	0.6521	25	0.8371	14
A9	0.6717	10	0.3290	5	0.9390	4	0.4720	22	0.6956	19	0.9803	4
A100.5654	19	0.1535	23	0.6831	16	0.5987	9	0.6218	28	0.8338	15	
A110.5208	26	0.2187	15	0.7395	5	0.5695	12	0.6347	27	0.8698	7	
A120.6257	12	0.3145	8	0.6736	22	0.5370	15	0.6699	23	0.8241	24	
A130.7484	6	0.3647	4	0.9658	3	0.5351	16	0.6522	24	0.9864	3	
A140.4442	33	0.1469	24	0.6708	25	0.6659	3	0.3240	35	0.8223	29	
A150.4917	29	0.1129	27	0.6700	26	0.3008	32	0.7636	5	0.8241	25	
A160.4959	28	0.0952	30	0.6737	21	0.4838	21	0.7025	17	0.8284	21	
A170.7560	5	0.1451	25	0.7340	6	0.5522	14	0.6895	21	0.8894	5	
A180.7801	4	0.0643	33	0.6890	12	0.6170	7	0.6043	29	0.8874	6	
A190.9979	2	0.7694	2	0.2244	35	0.3567	29	0.7521	7	0.4141	35	
A200.5156	27	0.2489	11	0.6840	15	0.5963	10	0.5776	30	0.8292	20	
A210.5739	16	0.2465	12	0.6693	28	0.5046	18	0.6899	20	0.8235	28	
A220.1892	35	0.0000	36	0.7194	9	0.6264	6	0.5379	33	0.8617	8	
A230.5536	22	0.0943	31	0.6708	24	0.5234	17	0.6762	22	0.8256	22	
A240.0000	36	0.0160	35	0.6901	11	0.7017	2	0.0000	36	0.8301	18	
A250.4829	31	0.1932	17	0.6715	23	0.3446	30	0.7417	9	0.8246	23	
A260.4655	32	0.1127	28	0.6693	29	0.4083	27	0.7263	12	0.8239	26	
A270.8125	3	0.3222	7	0.6868	13	0.5716	11	0.6369	26	0.8485	12	
A280.5649	20	0.2229	14	0.0000	36	0.4407	24	0.7029	16	0.0000	36	
A290.5634	21	0.1616	22	0.6659	32	0.4672	23	0.7134	14	0.8211	33	

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Table A.15: Comparative analysis (cont...)

2023						2022					
RAWEC		MARCOS		CORASO		RAWEC		MARCOS		CORASO	
Values	Ranking	Values	Ranking	Values	Ranking	Values	Ranking	Values	Ranking	Values	Ranking
A300.5502	23	0.1806	19	0.6657	33	0.3429	31	0.7473	8	0.8207	34
A310.6126	14	0.1910	18	0.6697	27	0.4900	20	0.7022	18	0.8236	27
A320.6641	11	0.1380	26	0.6817	17	0.6271	5	0.5412	32	0.8514	11
A330.4844	30	0.1693	21	0.6812	18	0.3571	28	0.7373	10	0.8304	17
A340.7015	9	0.3271	6	1.0000	1	0.2412	34	0.7629	6	1.0000	1
A350.3726	34	0.1010	29	0.7252	7	0.0000	36	0.7868	2	0.8554	10
A360.7322	7	0.3701	3	0.6798	19	0.2210	35	0.7677	3	0.8301	19